

Alcide d'Orbigny and the Paris Foraminifera: story of a collection under Byne attack

Miss Clara HAIRIE^{1,3}, Dr Annachiara Bartolini², Dr Marie-Béatrice Forel², Mrs Oulfa Belhadj¹, Dr Véronique Rouchon¹

¹Centre de Recherche sur la Conservation (CRC UAR3224) - Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, MC, CNRS, Paris, France, ²Centre de Recherche en Paléontologie - Paris (CR2P UMR7207) - Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, SU, CNRS, Paris, France, ³Institut Lavoisier de Versailles (ILV UMR8180) - UVSQ, CNRS, Versailles, France

G4: General, Lecture Theatre 3, Appleton Tower, 11 Crichton Street, EH8 9LE, June 7, 2022, 9:30 AM - 11:00 AM

In 1858, the National Museum of natural History, Paris, acquired the prestigious foraminiferal collection of the French naturalist Alcide Dessalines d'Orbigny (1802-1857). Pioneer in the fields of micropalaeontology and biostratigraphy, d'Orbigny's deep interest in tiny shells and micro-fossils led him to publish the first classification of the Phylum of Foraminifera in 1826. He later became the first professor of palaeontology at the Museum. However, quarrels in the teaching community resulted in multiple vacancies at the chair of palaeontology after d'Orbigny's death. His collection, which includes about 800 slides of type specimens, 3D sculptures enlarged 40-200 times, hundreds of "unpublished plates" and a thousand small bottles of sediments, was progressively abandoned. For almost a century, the foraminifera have been left to the care of scientists external to the museum. In 2007, a position of professor of micropalaeontology was finally created and micropalaeontological collections were gathered. Until then, the conditions of conservation of this outstanding scientific resource have been relatively unknown.

Today, the collection is threatened by Byne decay. About a fifth of the foraminifera is suffering from the development of white calcium-based efflorescence that fragilize the structure of the specimens. Presence of wooden-based materials can explain the emergence of the salts. Yet, the variety in the distribution and mineralogical nature of the crystals seems to indicate different degradation mechanisms linked to the storage conditions. Thereby, a key to understand the current state of the collection leans on its past. This presentation is thus an invitation to travel through time. It deals with the history of the collection care, taking advantage of the few testimonies (archives, photographs...) that reached us.

